

CHOOSING THE REINFORCEMENT IN A LAMINATED PLATE WITH AN OPEN HOLE

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ABSTRACT

The presence of an open hole in a laminated plate undergoing loading causes a stress concentration zone. Taking this zone into account, leads to an overdimensioning of the plate as a move away from the hole. In the case of an infinite plate with an open hole, the stress concentration coefficient, K_T is equal to three for an isotropic material and can reach ten for an anisotropic material.

In order to increase locally the strength ability of such a structure, it is possible to reinforce it, in the vicinity of the hole by inserting plies. The reinforcement under investigation is a set of annular fibre patterns obtained by filament winding. They are inserted in the laminate before polymerisation.

We propose a numerical approach to achieve the design of such a reinforcement by correcting a plane calculation thanks to the interlaminar stress determination. Experimental results allow the validation of this approach.

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED TO CHOOSE A FILAMENT REINFORCEMENT

We studied a plate with an opening having a radius called « a » and reinforced by annular reinforcements of inside radius called « a » and outside radius called « b », t_1 being the thickness of the reinforced zone while t_2 is the thickness of the plate. In order to determine the stress state of the various zones, numerical approaches using the finite element method have been conducted and we can refer to the literature [1], [2]. This type of three-dimensional calculation or pseudo three-dimensional calculation is difficult and time-consuming. Moreover, the singularity of stress features at the level of the free edge leads to convergence difficulties.

Figure 1. Geometry of the structure

The domain geometry (plate) and the loading investigated allow us to assume the case of a laminate undergoing plane stresses except in the free edge zone and except for a thickness change. The literature dealing with the problem of free edge and of ply insertion reinforcement, shows that zones with three-dimensional stresses are very localised. Moreover the stress field tends naturally to a two-dimensional solution as we move away from the zone previously mentioned. This remark takes us to choose particular numerical methods, permitting a global two-dimensional approach,

complemented by additional local studies instead of using a global three-dimensional approach, difficult to use. We notice various particular zones :

- a zone with a three-dimensional character
 - in the vicinity of the free edge
 - in the vicinity of the thickness variation
- a zone with a two-dimensional character
 - between the free edge and the end of the reinforcement
 - at a sufficient distance of the end of the reinforcement

An other approach to determine the stress state is to locally correct a C.L.T (Classical Laminate Theory) computation. As a matter of fact, this calculation does not verify the boundary conditions neither at the free edge, nor at the transition zone between the reinforced part and the non reinforced part of the plate. We thus suppose the existence of a three-dimensional stress field in the vicinity of the free edge, to re-establish the boundary conditions while the local equilibrium will be maintained. The interlaminar stresses are thus directly linked to σ_{yy} and σ_{xy} , which result from the C.L.T. calculation on the free edge.

P.BARJOSEPH [3] and YE [4] have shown that the C.L.T calculation corresponds to the 0 order of the asymptotic development of stresses by ply. This development being a function of the parameter $l = h/L$ where h is the thickness and L a characteristic length in the plate plane. From this, we can determine interlaminar stresses by solving a problem of generalised plane strains in semi-infinite bands perpendicular to the free edge. This approach shows the dependence between interlaminar and plane stresses. The correcting field of stresses hence determined and added to the C.L.T field, permits to verify the set of boundary conditions. TANG [5] used this method in the case of curved free edges, LECUYER [6] mentions that this method can be applied to loaded free edges. Yet, the transition zone between the reinforced and non reinforced parts of the plate can be modelled by a loaded free edge. We can thus determine for our geometry and our load, the stress fields. To do so, we associate the solution of a C.L.T problem with the solution of a generalised plane strain problem in semi-infinite bands which are perpendicular to the free edge.

We can approach in different ways the solution of a problem of generalised plane strains in order to study the correcting fields. Let us mention first, a semi-analytical method based on the study of LEKNITSKI potentials, then displacement finite element methods [7] as well as the use of a stress variational formulation [6] and [8].

To determine the stress correcting field we will use a complete method using statically admissible fields depending on one-dimensional discretisation by finite element in the plate thickness. This method has been validated and then marketed as CLEOPS [8].

Consequently we propose an alternative to a three-dimensional solution which requires heavy calculation tools and which requires also a case by case study. This alternative consists in an initial two-dimensional calculation. The plate is meshed with plate finite elements which are stressed in the plane on a simplified geometry. The simplest method does not take into account the geometry of thickness change. It models an abrupt thickness change, featured by a homogeneous behaviour different in the reinforced and non-reinforced zones. We can also model a step by step thickness change. The advantage of the C.L.T method with a simple modelling of the domain is to permit a parametering of the meshing. What differs from one case to the other is the law of the homogenised behaviour. This first step allows to define the total thickness of reinforcement to insert in the basic laminate as well as its mean outside radius in order to obtain a determined KT. A second step permits to deal more precisely with the reinforcement load mode which is unknown in the previous approach. The method which is proposed uses the asymptotic characteristic of the three-dimensional solution. It should optimise the reinforcement. The global thickness of the reinforcement can thus be divided (it is determined by the C.L.T approach) and annular reinforcements will be spread in the thickness according to an optimal stratification plane according to the following criteria :

- transfer zone size.
- minimisation of delamination risks in the transfer zone.
- minimisation of interlaminar stresses of free edge.

To validate the calculation procedure, we considered an isotropic plate reinforced by a pattern composed of circumferential winding. An analytical solution is given to us by Mc KENZIE studies[9]. We obtained a very good correlation between the analytical and numerical values.

DEFINITION AND DETERMINATION OF THE CRITERIA

We apply here separately, first a plane criterion of Tsai-Wu to assess the damages caused by matrix crack and fibre rupture and later, an interface criterion for the start of delamination.

In a laminate [0/45/-45]_s the stress σ_{xz} is essential and maximal at the interface between the plies at 0° and +45°. The stress σ_{zz} is maximal on the symmetry plane. The stress σ_{yz} is null on the edge and never reaches an important intensity. The most loaded angular sectors around the hole take place in the range from -60 à -80° and from 60 à 80° versus to the load direction. We use for the interface the quadratic criterion Eqn(1) with :

σ_{zz}^{Dc} (compression strength of the interface) $\gg \sigma_{zz}^{Dt}$ (tensile strength of the interface):

$$\left[\frac{1}{\sigma_{zz}^{Dt}} \right] \bar{\sigma}_{zz} + \left[\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^2 + \bar{\sigma}_{yz}^2}{\sigma_{xz}^{D2}} \right] \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

The shear stresses are gathered in a resultant.

There is a start of delamination if this expression is equal to 1. σ_{ij}^D is the start stress at the delamination.

The averaged stress expression is Eqn(2)

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \frac{1}{y} \int_0^y N_{xx} \sigma_{ij}^1(y, h) dy \quad (2)$$

y, being a characteristic distance of integration takes respectively the values y_0 et y_1 for shear and normal stresses. σ_{ij}^1 is the value of σ_{ij} for N_{xx} = unit value. LECUYER [10],[11] proposes a method to determine the characteristic distance y_0 et σ_{xz}^D , that is considered as intrinsic to the material and thus independent from the geometry.

RESULT ANALYSIS

From the C.L.T results, we can say that in that case, the reinforcement plays the given role. As a counterpart, a sensitive zone appears at the level of the external diameter on the reinforcement at 45°. Yet the C.L.T analysis is not sufficient. As a matter of fact, the values of plane stresses taken into account are erroneous at the vicinity of the free edge and at the vicinity of the end of the reinforced zone. An additional study, achieved with "CLEOPS" method, allows the analysis of edge effects and of the load transfer mechanism.

Due to coupling, the intensity of the correcting fields is directly proportional to the value of conditions at the limits. We find that at the level of the free edge, the interlaminar stresses are maximal at 90° from the loading direction but remain low compared to the ones located at the level of the limit of the reinforced zone. For this zone, the maximal values encountered are at 45° from the load direction.

We carried out a parametric study in order to know the influence $t1/t2$ and of b/a . We observe the variation of KT, stress concentration coefficient at the hole edge. As b/a increases, $KT = f(t1/t2)$ decreases. We note that this decrease is rapid for values of $t1/t2$ included between 1 and 4. To exceed this range does not seem to be interesting. The gain is no longer noticeable compared to the increase of matter and size. Moreover, beyond a KT reduction by two compared to the non-reinforced case, the limit of the reinforced zone is overloaded at 45°. As far as KT variations are concerned as a function of b/a , it does not seem interesting to exceed a variation zone included between 1 and 2, the gain becoming low compared the added matter. This study performed with a C.L.T calculation has shown the existence of two critical zones. The first one is located at the hole edge at 90°, the second one being located at the outside limit of the reinforced zone at 45° from the loading direction. The calculation of the R strength coefficient using a plane criterion shows on one hand, that at the level of the hole edge, R strength coefficient is a growing function of $t1/t2$ and of b/a and on the other hand that at the transfer zone, R strength coefficient is a growing function of b/a and a decreasing function of $t1/t2$.

This study presents many possible choices for combinations of $t1/t2$ and b/a to obtain a KT determined reduction at the hole edge. In an approach of optimisation, the choice should orientate as a function of two following objectives:

- to present balance of the load level of KT max zones and of the limit of the reinforced zone at 45°

- to minimise the transfer interlaminar stresses.

METHOD TO CHOOSE A REINFORCEMENT SIZE

To obtain a max gain (in relation to the non reinforced plate) on the KT (or on R) at the hole edge, the largest possible reinforcement should be chosen. If such a choice is done, the most stressed zone won't be the hole edge but the transfer zone. To determine the optimal reinforcement the couples (t_1/t_2 , b/a) should be investigated; these couples perform the balance of the two most stressed zones and then, among the couples, the one minimising the KT should be chosen. We called this technique « balancing ». Balancing of course should be performed, taking into consideration the stresses all over the laminated plies. This method permits to predimension the size of the reinforcement that is, its thickness and its diameters.

Figure 2 : Balancing of plies at 0° for a laminated (45, -45, 0)_s. G gain (black marks) on the R strength coefficient R and ΔR (white marks) for a = 40 mm

Figure 3 : Balancing of plies at 45° for a laminated (45, -45, 0)_s. G gain (white marks) on the R strength coefficient R and ΔR (black marks) for a = 40 mm

In the case of a laminate (+45, -45, 0)_s the most loaded pre-transfer zone is still located at 45°. As plies at +/- 45° et à 0° are not stressed similarly, the question is to define for which ply should balancing be performed. The two sets of plies cannot be balanced simultaneously. On Fig 2 et 3, we note that t_1/t_2 ratio at equilibrium depends strongly on b/a . Balancing of plies at 0° is reached

before the one of plies at 45°, as shown in Fig 2 et 3. On these figures: ΔR is the difference between the strength coefficient on one hand at the hole edge at 90° from the loading direction and on the other hand at the outside limit of the reinforcement 45° from the loading direction, G is the gain obtained at the threshold of the first damage versus the non reinforced case.

The improvement is important since we go from a 75% gain to a 90% gain for a small increase of t_1/t_2 ratio, increasing from 1.74 to 1.9. We slightly unbalance the plies at 0° while keeping a very high criterion. Finally, we verify that the reinforcement is globally less stressed than the basic laminate.

After determining the optimum volume of the reinforcement, reinforcement should spread in the laminate, that is to say it should be inserted in the stratification of the plate. The sum of thicknesses of annular reinforcements should correspond to the predefined thickness. For this, we calculate the interlaminar stresses and use quadratic interface criterion. Interlaminar stress calculation can be performed using "CLEOPS" software.

From these stresses and using an interface criterion, we can compare the different possible spreading pattern of the reinforcement.

From two examples, one dealing with a laminate composed of plies at 0°, +45°, and -45°, the second being with a laminate composed of 24 plies with a strong orientation at 0°, the following points can be mentioned:

- the interlaminar stresses of free edge are high and most important compared to the ones appearing in the load transfer zone
- the gain from the load of the first damage obtained by a C.L.T calculation is directly related to the reinforcement volume
- the stresses at the free edge level decrease as the gain increases
- the stresses appearing at the level of the transfer zone increase with the gain
- the multiplication of the number of annular reinforcements and the variations of their outside diameters contribute to minimising the delamination effects of the load transfer, through an intensity variation of interlaminar stresses and through the size of the transfer limit layer.

EXPERIMENTAL COMPARISON

The material used is a unidirectional prepreg of graphite epoxy HR(CTE2 35R 367) with a 0,331 mm thickness whose modules and strengths are given here: $E_x = 120$ Gpa; $E_y = E_z = 8,05$ Gpa; $E_s(G_{xy}) = E_q(G_{xz}) = 2,81$ Gpa; $E_p(G_{yz}) = 2,74$ Gpa; $X = 1670$ Mpa; $X' = 1400$ Mpa; $Y = 56$ Mpa; $Y' = 130$ Mpa; $S = 64$ MPa

The study of intrinsic parameters of delamination allowed us to identify the couple σ_{xz}^D ; y_0 which is characteristic of this material and permits to express the start criterion of delamination, in mode III : $\sigma_{xz}^D = 160$ Mpa and $0,14 \text{ mm} \leq y_0 \leq 0,16 \text{ mm}$

The samples are 320 mm long, $2l = 100$ mm wide and have a open hole with $2a = 20$ mm diameter. Dimensions were selected to meet the assumptions of calculation : $a/h \geq 5$ et $l/a \geq 5$. Length L was selected so that the transfer load of sample clamps will be outside of the reinforced zone. Samples have been achieved with the same stratification [0/45/-45]_s, for its sensitivity to interlaminar stresses, and reinforced by annular reinforcements with 30, 40, 50 mm diameters and 0,4 and 0,5 mm in thickness. The reinforcement position in the stacking has been determined by the calculation in order to show the reinforced solutions bringing gains different when compared with the non reinforced solution. Samples are subjected to tensile testing. Trials have been performed on a quasi-static machine controlled in displacement at a speed of 0,5 mm/mn. Each sample is fitted with two strain gages(a longitudinal one and a transverse one) at the edge of the hole (at 90° of load direction) and with a third longitudinal gage in the zone non affected by the hole and reinforcement. For each trial, we perform a follow-up by acoustic emission of sample damage.

COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPERIMENTS AND NUMERICAL CALCULATION

Calculations of minimum strength criteria have been performed in a plane mode at the start of delamination at the edge of a hole and at the limit of the transfer zone for each dimension of the reinforcement. We have shown during tensile rupture tests that delamination did happen at the

predicted criterion interfaces. Calculation is achieved for a traction 100 Mpa. The linearity hypothesis allows to deduce the value of the load causing the damage start for this criterion

The first damages which are detected by acoustic emission on the non reinforced sample correspond to a mean stress of 50 Mpa, whereas the ultimate rupture took place at 330 Mpa. The reinforced samples have shown a mean rupture stress which does not exceed 445 Mpa, this constitutes a gain lower than the one predicted through calculation. On the other hand, we have experienced an important increase of the stress (between 120 and 320 Mpa measured) corresponding to the start of the first damages for various reinforcement solutions.

Calculations show that delamination start at the hole edge limits the tensile loading of the reinforced plate with a hole. At the limit of the reinforced zone, criteria are not penalizing and furthermore, we should not fear delamination but damages in the plane. We witnessed no problem in the transfer zone for the tested samples.

The test goal was essentially to validate the trends shown by calculation. They have shown that the influence of the three factors t_1/t_2 , b/a as well as the reinforcement position were met.

A parametric analysis has shown that t_1/t_2 ratio decrease causes an interlaminar stress decrease thus leading to a strength coefficient increase. This is confirmed by the test results obtained on samples using reinforcements having the same diameter and position but with different thicknesses (respectively 0,5mm and 0,4mm).

For the b/a ratio, the parametric analysis shows that the increase of b/a ratio leads to an interlaminar stress reduction and consequently to a strength coefficient increase. Results confirm this trend.

The spreading of reinforcements inside the laminate improves strength in particular when we place an annular reinforcement between the ply at 0° and the ply at 45° . This calculation result is confirmed through experiments: the strength of samples with spread reinforcement are superior to the ones with outside reinforcements. We have noticed on the other hand that the deviation between the plane and interlaminar criteria diminishes when we insert a reinforcement between ply at 0° and ply at 45° , the plane criterion diminishes while the interlaminar one increases. It shows the positive influence of the reinforcement insert on the interlaminar stresses. Yet, according to calculations, interlaminar criterion remains determining but less significantly for samples with spread reinforcements. This can explain a separation of annular patterns provided they are outside the plate (photo 1) and can also explain too clear ruptures at the level of the hole on spread reinforcement samples (photo 2).

The ultimate rupture for all reinforced samples is about 35% higher than for non reinforced samples with a hole. This does not confirm the expected gain of more than 100% given through calculation. This deviation does not contradict the calculation method but shows the limit of linear calculation which stops at the first damages and thus does not report the ultimate rupture. A damage model is required to continue calculation up to this value. The first detected damages through an acoustic emission report better gain obtained thanks to reinforcement.

CONCLUSION

We have shown that the reinforcement of a plate with an open hole placing annular patterns with circumferential fibre orientation, diminished the concentration of stresses at the edge of the hole. This reinforcement caused also an increase of the stresses at the limit of the reinforced zone in an area situated at 45° of the load direction, hence giving a concept of balance between these two zones. Through a plane calculation, we define the size of the reinforcements in order to obtain an identical strength in the two zones. Calculations show clearly that shearing permits load transfer. The spreading of the reinforcement in the stacking is favourable since it multiplies the number of active interfaces for the transfer. This decreases the maximal interlaminar stresses and scales down the limit layer size. The method which is used aims at avoiding 3D calculations which are too time-consuming. We have thus chosen a simplified structure representation : a plate with two different layers linked by continuous plies of the basic laminate. The use of plate theory is justified by asymptotic methods. The 2D approximate quality depends on t_1/a and t_1/L parameters which must remain small. In reality, we verified afterward the decay of limit layer correctors. Taking into account the difficulty to obtain general design rules, we turn to a systematic calculation of each laminate. Yet the model which is proposed logically includes :

- the dependence of gain with the reinforcement volume by applying a plane criterion at the reinforced area and a start criterion of delamination at the edge of the hole.
- the reinforcement limit by the loading of an area at 45° at the limit of the reinforcement zone.
- the role of active interface number and the role of the step by step diameter variation on the alleviation of transfer effects.

We encounter two difficulties :

- a poor assessment of the influence of edge effects on the start of the first damages. In addition we do not possess global reliable criteria and furthermore the coupling phenomena are not well controlled.
- the problem complexity after the beginning of the first damages. Presently only partial solutions will be proposed.

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Fig 4 tensile test on a sample with two annular reinforcements R of 0,5 mm thickness and 40 and 50 mm diameter

photography 1

photography 2